

WHEAT STRAW COMPOSITION AND SPECTRAL REFLECTANCE CHANGES DURING DECOMPOSITION

C.S.T. Daughtry¹, Guy Serbin², J.B. Reeves III³, P.C. Doraiswamy¹, and E.R. Hunt Jr.¹

¹USDA-ARS Hydrology and Remote Sensing Laboratory, Beltsville, Maryland 20705 USA

²ASRC Management Services, USDA-FAS Office of Global Analysis, Washington, DC USA

³USDA-ARS Environmental Management and Byproduct Utilization Laboratory, Beltsville, MD, USA

ABSTRACT

Quantification of crop residue cover is required to assess the extent of conservation tillage. Our objectives were to measure the changes in wheat straw composition and spectral reflectance during decomposition and to assess impact of these changes on remotely sensed estimates of residue cover. Mesh bags filled with wheat straw were placed on the soil surface and removed at intervals over 22 months. The relative proportions of cellulose and hemicellulose in the straw declined while lignin increased. Reflectance spectra of wheat straw and two soils were measured over 350-2500 nm region. Absorption features in the reflectance spectra associated with cellulose diminished as the straw decomposed. The Cellulose Absorption Index (CAI) was a robust estimator of crop residue cover. Advanced multi-spectral sensors with multiple relatively narrow shortwave infrared bands or hyperspectral sensors are needed to assess crop residue cover reliably over diverse agricultural landscapes.

Index Terms— Crop residue cover, Lignin, Cellulose, Reflectance spectra, Cellulose Absorption Index

1. INTRODUCTION

Crop residues or plant litter is the portion of a crop left in the field after harvest. Management of crop residues is an integral part of most conservation tillage systems. Crop residues on the soil surface provide a protective barrier against water and wind erosion and reduce the amount of soil, nutrients, and pesticides that reaches streams and rivers [7]. Crop residues also contribute soil organic matter which improves soil quality and sequesters carbon. The overall result is less soil erosion and improved soil and water quality. Soil tillage and residue harvesting for bio-energy are management practices that reduce crop residue cover.

Quantification of crop residue cover is required to evaluate the effectiveness and extent of conservation tillage practices. The standard technique for measuring mean crop residue cover in fields is the line-point transect method [10].

Regional assessments of conservation tillage practices based on annual roadside surveys of crop residue levels after planting are compiled for selected counties. However, these surveys are subjective and the techniques vary from county to county [3].

Traditional remote sensing approaches for assessing crop residue cover have had mixed success because crop residues and soils are spectrally similar and often differ only in amplitude in the visible and near infrared wavelengths [2, 11]. An alternative approach is based on detecting an absorption feature near 2100 nm that is associated with cellulose [1, 8]. The feature is evident in reflectance spectra of dry crop residues and is absent in spectra of soils [2, 11]. The relative intensity of this feature in reflectance spectra is linearly related to crop residue cover using ground-based [2, 4], aircraft [5], and satellite [3] hyperspectral sensors.

The erosion protection afforded by crop residues on the soil surface diminishes as they decompose and lose both mass and cover. As the chemical and physical properties of crop residues change during decomposition, their spectral reflectance properties also change which could affect the ability of remote sensing methods to assess residue cover.

Our objectives were to measure and model the changes in wheat straw fiber composition and spectral reflectance during decomposition and to assess impact these changes on remotely sensed estimates of residue cover.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Experiment Design.

Winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) was grown in a production field at the USDA-ARS Beltsville Agricultural Research Center near Beltsville, Maryland. After the wheat was harvested for grain on 22 July 2006, samples of the straw were collected.

Approximately 500 g of straw was placed in 0.7 x 0.9 m black fiberglass mesh (1.1 x 1.3 mm openings) bags. The bags plus straw were sealed, dried at 50 C, and weighed. On 1 August 2006, the bags were staked securely on the soil surface in a field previously planted to wheat and double-cropped with soybeans (*Glycine max* Merr.). The bags were

arranged in six clusters in a randomized complete block design (2 moisture levels and 3 blocks). Three clusters of bags (wet treatment) received 4 mm of supplemental irrigation twice daily from 3 August to 12 October 2006 and from 16 July to 15 October 2007 while the remaining clusters of bags (dry treatment) received only normal precipitation. Daily minimum and maximum air temperatures and precipitation were recorded at a weather station within 0.3 km.

After 0, 57, 136, 212, 325, 419, and 522 days, one bag was removed from each cluster ($n=6$), air-dried in a greenhouse, and stored. At the completion of the experiment on day 673, the remaining bags ($n=18$) were removed from the field. All bags were dried at 50 C and weighed.

2.2. Reflectance Measurements

Samples of dried wheat straw from each bag were placed to a 2 cm depth in 45-cm square trays that were painted flat black. Duplicate trays were prepared. Reflectance spectra were acquired with a spectroradiometer (FieldSpec Pro, Analytical Spectral Devices, Boulder, Colorado USA) over the 350 to 2500 nm wavelength region at 1 nm intervals. The samples were illuminated by six 100-W quartz-halogen lamps mounted on the arms of a camera copy stand at 45 cm over the sample at a 45° illumination zenith angle. A current-regulated DC power supply stabilized the output of the lamps. The 18° fore-optic of the spectroradiometer were aligned and positioned 60 cm from the sample surface at a 0° view zenith angle. The diameter of the field of view of the spectroradiometer was 19 cm. The illumination and view angles were chosen to minimize shadowing and to emphasize the fundamental spectral properties of the samples. Four spectra of 50 scans each were acquired from each sample by rotating the sample tray 90° after each spectrum. A 61-cm square Spectralon (Labsphere, Inc, North Sutton, New Hampshire USA) reference panel was placed in the field of view and illuminated and viewed in the same manner as the samples. Reflectance factors were calculated and corrected for the reflectance of the Spectralon reference panel.

Reflectance spectra were also acquired of soils with minor modifications. The 8° fore optic was used which resulted in an 8.5 cm diameter field of view. The agricultural top soils were Loring (fine-silty, mixed, active, thermic Oxyaquic Fragiudalfs) from Como, Mississippi; and Sverdrup (sandy mixed, frigid, Typic Hapludolls) from Morris, Minnesota. Each soil was oven-dried at 105° C, crushed to pass a 2-mm screen, and placed to a depth of 1 cm in 20-cm diameter sample trays.

The intrinsic spectral vegetation index, Normalized Difference Index (NDI5) [9] was calculated as: $NDI5 = (TM4 - TM5)/(TM4 + TM5)$, where TM4 and TM5

refer to Landsat TM band 4 (760-900 nm) and band 5 (1550-1750 nm). The Cellulose Absorption Index (CAI) was calculated as: $CAI = 100(0.5(R_{2.0} + R_{2.2}) - R_{2.1})$, where $R_{2.0}$, $R_{2.1}$, and $R_{2.2}$ refer to reflectance values in 10-nm bands centered at 2030 nm, 2100 nm, and 2210 nm, respectively [2].

2.3. Fiber Analyses

Samples of wheat straw from each bag were ground to pass a 1-mm screen. Neutral detergent fiber (NDF), acid detergent fiber (ADF), hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin were determined [6] as modified by Ankom Technology (http://www.ankom.com/09_procedures/procedures.shtml). Briefly, 0.5 g of ground wheat straw was placed in a filter bag, heat sealed, and extracted successively with neutral detergent solution, acid detergent solution, and 72% H₂SO₄. Dry weights were recorded between each extraction. Fiber composition was corrected for ash content of the wheat straw. All chemical assay results were the average of triplicate determinations.

2.4. Data Analysis

2.4.1 Decomposition Days

The concept of decomposition days was used to normalize time based on climatic conditions assuming that the most important environmental factors for decomposition are temperature and moisture [12]. Each coefficient was constrained from 0 to 1, with 1 indicating optimum conditions for microbial activity (maximum decomposition) and 0 indicating no microbial activity (no decomposition). When the bags of straw were irrigated, the moisture coefficient was set to 1. Decomposition days (DD) for each treatment were accumulated based on the minimum of the temperature coefficient or the moisture coefficient for each day. First-order exponential decomposition rates were determined using $M_t/M_0 = \exp^{-k(DD)}$, where M_t is the biomass at time t , M_0 is the initial biomass, k is the decomposition coefficient ($g\ g^{-1}\ DD^{-1}$), and DD is the decomposition days [13].

2.4.2. Statistical Analyses.

The wheat straw composition data were empirically connected with the spectral reflectance data using Pearson correlation for single wavelengths and stepwise regression for multiple wavelengths. In addition, major absorption features in vegetation reflectance spectra were delineated (i.e., 408-518 nm, 588-750 nm, 1116-1284 nm, 1634-1786 nm, 2006-2196 nm, and 2222-2378 nm) and continuum removal techniques were employed [1, 8]. For each major absorption feature, band depth was normalized to the wavelength at the center of the absorption feature (BNC) or to the area of the absorption feature (BNA).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Decomposition days at Beltsville were limited by moisture at some times of the year and temperature at others. Temperature was the limiting factor when supplemental irrigation was applied. Supplemental irrigation was applied for only 181 of the 673 days of the experiment but the irrigation treatment nearly doubled the cumulative DD compared to DD for normal precipitation.

The fraction of dry mass remaining in the bags declined as a function of decomposition days (Fig. 1). Irrigation did not significantly affect slopes of the decline in dry mass remaining because of the normalization of DD. When both wet and dry treatments were fitted with a single line, the intercept was not significant. The slope of the decline in biomass or k value was less than those reported for field observations of high density winter wheat residues [12, 13]. The residue layer in the mesh bags was quite thick (~10 cm initially) and had limited contact with the soil where conditions for decomposition were most favorable to decomposition. Highest decompositions rates were observed in the low density treatments where a high proportion of the residue elements were in direct contact with the soil. Supplemental irrigation significantly enhanced the disappearance of the wheat straw mass and provided a method to stimulate decomposition in the field.

The wheat straw mass did not disappear uniformly (Fig. 2). Some components of the straw disappeared more rapidly than others. The relative proportions of hemicellulose, and cellulose in the wheat straw declined significantly as a function of DD while the relative proportion of lignin in the straw significantly increased (more than doubled).

The reflectance spectra of dry wheat straw at selected DD (Fig 3) illustrate the subtle changes in spectrum shape as the wheat straw decomposes. These spectra lack the chlorophyll and water absorptions that dominate the spectra of green leaves [1]. Structural components (cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin) of the wheat straw dominate the spectrum of each sample at wavelengths >1300 nm. The intensities of the cellulose and lignin absorption features near 2100 and 2300 nm diminished as the wheat straw decomposed. The relative intensity of the absorption feature near 2100 nm, defined as the cellulose absorption index (CAI), is linearly related to crop residue cover [2, 3, 5].

The correlations between wheat straw composition and reflectance spectra are presented as correlograms in Figure 4. Reflectance near 1710, 2100 and 2350 nm were strongly correlated with the concentration of hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin [1]. High correlations in the visible and near

Figure 1. (left) Fractions of wheat straw mass remaining as a function of decomposition days.

Figure 2. (right) Changes in the composition of wheat straw as a function of decomposition days.

infrared wavelengths (400-1300 nm) were probably associated with overall decrease in straw reflectance (Fig. 3) rather than a specific fiber component.

In order to assess the impact of crop residue decomposition on the detection of crop residue cover, the reflectance of mixed scenes with various proportions of crop residue and soils was simulated using linear combinations of reflectance factors [4]. The mineral absorption feature near 2200 nm was evident in the spectrum of each bare soil ($fR=0$ in Fig 5), but was attenuated as residue cover increased. The fresh straw was darker than the Loring soil, but brighter than the Sverdrup soil (Fig 5A, 5C). As the residue decomposed, differences in reflectance increased for the Loring soil, but diminished for the Sverdrup soil (Fig 5B, 5D).

Residue covers for simulated scenes of four ages of wheat straw on Loring and Sverdrup soils are plotted as functions of two spectral residue indices (Fig. 6). These contrasting soils produced minor changes in the bare soil ($fR=0$) values for CAI (Fig. 6A, 6C), but large relative shifts in bare soil values for NDI5 (Fig. 6B, 6D). The slopes of residue cover vs CAI were relatively constant for both soils. As crop residues decompose, the slope of residue cover vs

CAI also changed slightly. However, the slopes of residue cover vs NDI5 from negative to positive as the soil background changed and positive to negative as the residues aged. Nevertheless, NDI5 may be effective for scenes with limited variations in soil properties.

These results indicate that current broad-band, multispectral imaging systems will not provide robust estimates of crop residue cover when soils and residues are

variable. Advanced multispectral sensors with multiple, relatively narrow shortwave infrared bands or hyperspectral sensors are needed to assess crop residue cover reliably over diverse agricultural landscapes.

4. REFERENCES

[1] Curran, P.J., Dungan, J.L., Peterson, D.L.. Estimating the foliar biochemical concentration of leaves with reflectance spectrometry: Testing the Kokaly and Clark methodologies. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 76:349-359. 2001.

[2] Daughtry, C.S.T. Discriminating crop residues from soil by shortwave infrared reflectance. *Agronomy J.*93:125-131. 2001.

[3] Daughtry, C.S.T., Doraiswamy, P.C., Hunt Jr., E.R., Stern, A.J., McMurtrey III, J.E., and Prueger, J.H. Assessing crop residue cover and soil tillage intensity. *Soil Tillage Research.*91:101-108. 2006.

[4] Daughtry, C.S.T. and Hunt Jr., E.R. Mitigating the effects of soil and residue water contents on remotely sensed estimates of crop residue cover. *Remote Sensing of Environment.*112:1647-1657. 2008.

[5] Daughtry, C.S.T., Hunt Jr., E.R., Doraiswamy, P.C., and McMurtrey III, J.E. Remote sensing the spatial distribution of crop residues. *Agronomy J.*97:864-871. 2005.

[6] Goering, H.K. and Van Soest, P.J. Forage fiber analyses. *USDA Agriculture Handbook No.379.* 1970.

[7] Lal, R., Kimble, J.M., Follett, R.F., Cole, C.V. The potential of U.S. cropland to sequester carbon and mitigate the greenhouse effect. 128 p. Lewis Publishers, Boca Raton, FL. 1999.

[8] Kokaly, R.F. and Clark, R.N. Spectroscopic determination of leaf biochemistry using band-depth analysis of absorption features and stepwise multiple linear regression. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 67:267-287. 1999.

[9] McNairn, H., and Protz, R. Mapping corn residue cover on agricultural fields in Oxford County, Ontario, using Thematic mapper. *Can J. Remote Sensing* 19:152-159. 1993.

[10] Morrison, J.E., Jr., Huang, C., Lightle, D.T., and Daughtry, C.S.T. Residue cover measurement techniques. *J. Soil Water Conservation* 48: 479-483. 1993.

[11] Serbin, Guy, Daughtry, C.S.T., Hunt Jr., E.R., and Brown, D.J. Effect of soil on remote sensing of crop residue cover. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* (in press) 2009.

[12] Steiner, J.L., Schomberg, H.H., Douglas Jr., C.L., and Black, A.L. Standing stem persistence in no-tillage small-grain fields. *Agronomy J.*86:76-81. 1994.

[13] Steiner, J.L., Schomberg, H.H., Unger, P.W., and Cresap, J. Crop residue decomposition in no-tillage small-grain fields. *Soil Sci.Soc.Am.J.*63:1817-1824. 1999.

Figure 3. (left) Reflectance spectra of wheat straw for various decomposition days. The spectra are displaced vertically to avoid overlap. Reflectance at 1300 nm is provided for each spectrum.

Figure 4. (right) Correlograms for wheat straw components and reflectance spectra. Dotted vertical lines at 1710, 2100, and 2310 nm.

Figure 5 Reflectance spectra of simulated mixtures of wheat residue and soil. Residue cover (fR) ranged from bare soil (fR=0) to full residue cover (fR=1).

Figure 6. Responses of two spectral residue indices (CAI and NDI5) to changes in wheat residue cover on two soils.